

From the Ottoman Empire to the Republic: Military Struggles and Coups

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the nature of coups from the Ottoman period to the Republican era and to analyze the groups that carried them out. The article seeks to understand the tradition of coups in the Ottoman Empire and to compare it with the pattern of military interventions in the Republic of Turkey.

Keywords: Ottoman Empire, struggles for the throne, dynastic conflicts, palace coups, Janissary revolts, Ottoman modernization, 19th-century Ottoman politics, military coups in Turkey

Entrance

A coup d'état refers to the unlawful overthrow of a political authority, bureaucracy, or government by the armed forces. Violence is an inevitable reality of coups. They generally originate from the military wing within the state apparatus. Rather than eliminating the system itself, a coup typically replaces the individuals in power within that system. This feature is considered the primary distinction between a coup and a revolution. Compared to revolutions, coups usually result in far more limited structural change.

Throughout many periods of the Ottoman Empire, numerous coups led by military figures occurred. Some were driven solely by struggles for power, while others were justified in the name of preserving the state, even to the extent of opposing one's own father. In certain cases, coups emerged as a consequence of military disobedience.

The history of coups is well-developed within both Turkish aristocratic traditions and Latin political history. In Latin societies, this development can be attributed to strong street movements and the emergence of a distinct military elite class. In the Turkish context, particularly during the beylik period, coups stemmed from the military origins of political authority and the ambition for power.

The underlying causes of coups generally arise from political conflict or the perception that certain aspects of governance are failing; these constitute the central driving factors. From a modern perspective, coups are often linked to the loss of legitimacy of civilian governments. In the Ottoman Empire, however, coups did not occur for this reason. Instead, they typically resulted from conflicts among interest groups or dynastic struggles for the throne. The sultanate was extremely powerful, and the civilian population remained loyal to the ruling dynasty, which was widely regarded as legitimate.

In the Turkish case, the loss of governmental legitimacy in the eyes of the public began during the Republican period. Historically, this process is often associated with 1960. As a result of the Democrat Party's suppression of the Republican People's Party, the military perceived that civilian political authority had lost its legitimacy.¹

¹Ozan O. Varol, "The Democratic Coup d'État," *Harvard International Law Journal* 53, no. 2 (2012): 322–31.

Ottoman and Republican Turkey experienced coups for different underlying reasons. In the Ottoman era, power struggles were largely shaped by rival factions within the military, members of the ulema, and the broader *ilmiye* class competing for influence. By contrast, during the Republican period, interventions were generally framed as efforts to safeguard the political system. From the military's perspective, certain democratic outcomes were believed to create blockages within the state structure, a perception that, at times, paved the way for military intervention. Meanwhile, some groups interpreted these developments as the result of foreign interference.

Throne Struggles and Succession Conflicts in the Ottoman State Tradition

Although not always considered coups in the modern sense, the early Ottoman period witnessed intense struggles over succession. It is often stated that the first dispute over the throne occurred between Osman Gazi and his uncle. Later, the son of Murad I, with the backing of the Byzantine Empire, rebelled against his father; however, the uprising failed and he was executed.

Following Murad I's death at the Battle of Kosovo, leading statesmen reportedly urged Prince Bayezid to eliminate his brother, Prince Yakup Çelebi. Yakup thus became the first Ottoman prince to be executed as a result of an internal power struggle. In the centuries that followed, dynastic rivalries resurfaced periodically. Numerous princes, at times supported by military factions within the state and even by Byzantium, launched repeated rebellions in pursuit of the throne.²

The defeat at the Battle of Ankara and the subsequent capture of Bayezid I created a profound power vacuum within the Ottoman state. This absence of central authority triggered a fierce struggle for supremacy among his four sons. The first major confrontation took place between Mehmed Çelebi and İsa Çelebi. Mehmed emerged victorious and had his brother executed.

In the following phase, Mehmed sought to weaken the authority of Süleyman Çelebi, who had established control in Rumelia. To this end, he sent Musa Çelebi to the region. Musa soon rebelled, defeated Süleyman, and had him killed, after which he proclaimed himself ruler in Edirne.

Unlike Mehmed, however, Musa did not pursue a policy of balance with the Byzantine Empire. Instead, he attempted to lay siege to Constantinople, a move that disrupted the fragile political equilibrium. His stance also alienated sections of the military elite and the Rumelian beys. Anticipating that an increasingly aggressive policy would leave the state diplomatically isolated, Mehmed secured Byzantine support and moved against his brother. Musa was overthrown and executed, paving the way for the consolidation of Mehmed's rule.³

In principle, all princes—regardless of age—were considered to share a legitimate claim to the throne. In earlier periods, in order to manage potential disputes, Ottoman rulers had at times

² Ekrem Buğra Ekinci, "Osmanlı Hukukunda Şehzâde Katli" [The Execution of Princes in Ottoman Law], *Bayburt Üniversitesi İlahiyat Fakültesi Dergisi* 1, no. 1 (2015): 97.

³ Birkay Köse and Meryem Peker, "Fetret Devrinde Osmanlı (1402–1413): Fâsıla-i Saltanat" [The Ottoman Interregnum (1402–1413): The Interruption of Sovereignty], 6–17.

distributed imperial territories among their sons. Drawing on this historical precedent, Cem Sultan later challenged the prevailing succession practice.

Mehmed II introduced the **Kanunname-i Âl-i Osman**, a legal code that, in the interest of *nizam-ı âlem*—the preservation of public order and the continuity of the state—sanctioned fratricide. The measure was justified as a means of preventing prolonged civil strife and safeguarding imperial stability.

After Mehmed II's death, however, the empire was drawn into a serious internal conflict between Cem Sultan and Bayezid II. The struggle lasted for years and significantly strained the state. In fact, prior to Mehmed's legal reform, there had existed a contrasting tradition known as *ülüş*, a custom with roots extending back to the Göktürk Khaganate. According to this older understanding, sovereignty and territory could be apportioned among members of the ruling family.

In this context, Cem Sultan proposed dividing the empire between himself and Bayezid. Bayezid rejected the offer. Following his defeat, Cem sought refuge abroad and eventually died in exile in the Kingdom of Naples. His burial place remains uncertain.⁴

Yavuz Sultan Selim and the First Major Palace Coup

This was the greatest proof that being close to the capital was not enough to become a sultan. Sultan Bayezid II was ill. Due to his illness, he had delegated authority to his viziers and did not interfere much in state affairs. For this reason, rumors began to spread that Bayezid II would abdicate the throne. The struggle for the throne continued quietly until 1509, when his illness worsened.

Upon this, Bayezid II told the Grand Vizier Hadım Ali Pasha and Koca Mustafa Pasha that political support was in favor of Şehzade Ahmed. Şehzade Ahmed was a peaceful man like his father, and certain groups within the state administration were very pleased with this. The reason was that he followed a policy that avoided war; however, this situation was harming the state. In fact, during official meetings held in Edirne, they praised Şehzade Ahmed by comparing him to his father.⁵

As a result, Yavuz Sultan Selim went to İstanbul to visit his father. He left the sanjak of Trabzon to his son. After the visit, he crossed into Rumeli without his father's permission, made contact with the Janissaries, and gained the support of those who were dissatisfied with Şehzade Ahmed.

Thanks to this, Selim—who had been seen as the weakest candidate—rose to become the strongest contender. As a result, Şehzade Ahmed came to İstanbul to ascend the throne, but the Janissaries did not allow him to enter the city.⁶

As a result, not wanting bloodshed or the fragmentation of the state, Bayezid II decided to abdicate the throne and summoned his son Yavuz Sultan Selim from Kefe to İstanbul, handing over the throne to him.

4 Ekrem Buğra Ekinci, "Osmanlı Hukukunda Şehzâde Katli" [*The Execution of Princes in Ottoman Law*], *Bayburt Üniversitesi İlahiyat Fakültesi Dergisi* 1, no. 1 (2015): 96–100.

5 *Tevarih-i Âl-i Osman*, Berlin Staatsbibliothek, Ms. Orient 821, fols. 196b–197.

6 Uluçay, "Yavuz Sultan Selim Nasıl Padişah Oldu?" [*How Did Yavuz Sultan Selim Become Sultan?*], 75–76.

Şehzade Selim was now Sultan Selim⁷

After ascending the throne, Yavuz Sultan Selim had Şehzade Ahmed and his sons executed by strangulation for the survival of the state.

Yavuz Sultan Selim's deposition of his father was not for his own power, but for the interests of the state. Bayezid II was near death, and the threat of the Safavid Empire was increasing day by day. The state officials failed to recognize this danger and continued their peaceful policies. These peaceful policies were so misguided that they led to Kızılbaş rebellions within the country, which spread as far as Kütahya. Şehzade Ahmed was implementing the same policies as his father. At that time, the state's policy needed to be firm rather than peaceful. Yavuz carried this out in what he believed to be the most effective way. For the survival of the state, he enforced the practice of fratricide derived from the Kanunname-i Âl-i Osman.

There are also claims that Yavuz Sultan Selim killed his father; however, these claims are entirely fabricated. Such an event is not found in either Ottoman or foreign sources. Yes, Yavuz Sultan Selim deposed his father through a coup, but he did so by taking the throne in a way that did not harm him. In fact, Yavuz Sultan Selim ascended the throne after kissing his father's hand.

Afterward, Bayezid II took with him Rumelia Beylerbeyi Yunus Pasha, to whom he felt close, and his former treasurer Kasım Pasha, and told his son that he wished to go to Dimetoka. Sultan Selim Han fulfilled this request and allowed him to depart.⁸

The Incident of Genç Osman (1622)

Osman II, known as Genç Osman, ascended the throne during one of the most complex periods of the empire. At that time, the "cage system" (kafes) was being implemented in the Ottoman dynasty, and many princes had been executed despite this system. This situation weakened central authority. Genç Osman was aware of this and took steps to strengthen it.

One of the forces that most destabilized central authority was the Janissary Corps. With the collapse of the devshirme system, recruitment into the corps began to take place from among the local population of İstanbul. This led to a decline in discipline within the army. The Janissaries rejected military reforms and, in addition, went into cities and oppressed the population. As they grew wealthier, they also became involved in trade.

Genç Osman wanted to abolish this corps and establish in its place a more modern, merit-based, and contemporary military structure—similar to the concept of a national army in France. However, interest groups would not allow this. Not only the Janissaries but also factions within the palace were disturbed by attempts to abolish the corps.⁹

⁷ Faruk Söylemez, "Yavuz Sultan Selim'in Taht Mücadelesi" [*Yavuz Sultan Selim's Struggle for the Throne*], *Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, no. 33 (2012/2): 33.

⁸ Celalzade Mustafa, *Selimnâme* [The Selimnâme], 99.

⁹ İlker Gedik and Zehra Gedik, "Genç Osman'ın Reformist Vizyonu: Osmanlı Merkezîyetçiliği ve Yeniçeri Direnci" [Genç Osman's Reformist Vision: Ottoman Centralization and Janissary Resistance], *Akademik Tarih ve Düşünce Dergisi* 12, no. 1 (2025): 366–69.

This was because bureaucratic roles would change, and the palace was disturbed by this prospect. For this reason, they leaked Genç Osman's plan, and when the rebellion broke out, this bureaucratic group merely stood by and watched. Some factions even assisted the rebels.

As a result, on 20 May 1622, Osman II—only 17 years old at the time—was killed by the Janissary Corps.

This situation boosted the morale of the viziers and led them to train and raise their own household retainers (*kapı halkı*) in the provinces. The men trained by the viziers were given influential and powerful positions in the sanjaks and provinces, increasing their authority in regional administration.¹⁰ This development did not remain limited to the provinces; in the palace as well, the household networks of the viziers gained importance and began to occupy powerful bureaucratic positions, while the palace Janissaries were pushed into the background.

Köprülü Mehmed Pasha and his household were a family loyal to the Ottoman dynasty. They had become a highly influential bureaucratic family in Rumelia, Damascus, and Aleppo. With their growing power between 1683 and 1703, this family played a decisive role in the deposition of Mehmed IV and Mustafa II, and in the enthronement of Ahmed II, Suleiman II, and Ahmed III.

Mehmed IV was politically weak in terms of power under the dominance of the Köprülüs and sought to restore the dynasty's former legitimacy. Fate seemed to favor him in 1683 with the failed siege led by Merzifonlu Kara Mustafa Pasha during the Second Siege of Vienna. After the unsuccessful campaign, Mehmed IV had Kara Mustafa Pasha executed and confiscated his property.¹¹ Mehmed IV's struggle with the Köprülüs did not come to an end. The son of Köprülü Mehmed Pasha, Fazıl Mustafa Pasha, organized a military conspiracy to depose Mehmed IV. He sought to remove him through a military uprising.

In response, Mehmed IV attempted to appoint Fazıl Pasha as *kaymakam* (deputy governor) in İstanbul; however, as a consequence of the ensuing power struggle, Mehmed IV's sons, Mustafa II and Ahmed III, were confined to the Şimşirlik Apartments in Topkapı Palace. Meanwhile, figures close to the Köprülüs took positions within the cabinet of Suleiman II.¹²

When Suleiman II was near death, the Köprülüs—fearing that the sons of Mehmed IV might ascend the throne—sought to determine the choice of the next sultan themselves. As a result, with the support of the Köprülüs, Mehmed IV's brother, the relatively weak-seeming Ahmed II, ascended the throne.

Immediately after his accession, Fazıl Mustafa Pasha became grand vizier; however, his tenure was short-lived, as he was killed in 1691 during the Battle of Slankamen. Afterward, individuals closely aligned with the same faction successively assumed the grand vizierate.

¹⁰Abou-El-Haj, *The Rebellion of 1703* (City: Publisher, Year), 89.

¹¹ Tahir Sevinç, "Mustafa'nın İktidar Mücadelesi ve 1703 Edirne İsyanıyla Tahttan İndirilmesi" [Mustafa's Struggle for Power and His Deposition during the 1703 Edirne Rebellion], *Osmanlı Mirası Araştırmaları Dergisi (OMAD)* 4, no. 9 (July 2017): 25–42.

¹² For the confiscation of Merzifonlu Kara Mustafa Pasha in Belgrade, see Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye Ottoman Archives (BOA), D.BŞM-MHF 4/84, 12 Şaban 1095 [25 July 1684], fol. 2.

When Mustafa II ascended the throne in 1695, he was aware that both in the center and in the provinces, many of the trained household networks (*kapılar*) stemmed from the Köprülü base. Between 1695 and 1697, the sultan undertook efforts to alter this balance of power. He aimed to break the monopoly that the Köprülüs and other pasha factions held over official positions in both provincial and central administration. In line with this policy, he was careful to appoint statesmen of military and palace origin to the highest levels of government, favoring those trained in the palace center over figures emerging from the traditional provincial networks.

Indeed, his decision to appoint Elmas Mehmed Pasha—who was of palace origin—as grand vizier instead of Sürmeli Ali Pasha, who had risen through pasha households, was a clear indication of this policy. Through these reforms in central administration, Mustafa II sought to diminish the decisive influence of vizierial and pasha households over the state.¹³

In response, the Köprülüs attempted to block these efforts. During this process, they took control—contrary to waqf (pious endowment) law—of the foundations of Köprülü Mehmed Pasha and Fazıl Ahmed Pasha, which were under the supervision of the valide sultan and the şeyhülislam, together with Numan, the son of the martyred grand vizier Fazıl Mustafa Pasha. As justification, they claimed that the waqfs in Rumelia had fallen into enemy hands and those in Anatolia had been attacked by bandits. However, Feyzullah Efendi ruled this action contrary to waqf law and had the foundations officially confiscated and registered.

Mustafa II, unlike his uncles, had not been raised in confinement within the palace; he was a well-equipped and capable ruler. He had gained experience during the reign of Mehmed IV. His childhood tutor, Seyyid Feyzullah Efendi, was one of the few people he trusted. Mustafa II appointed him as şeyhülislam and later relied on him as a political advisor. Distrusting the cadres of previous periods, the sultan sought to build central authority through officials loyal to himself.

Following the example of Suleiman the Magnificent, Mustafa II personally joined military campaigns; however, this policy ended in defeat at the Battle of Zenta in 1697. Afterward, he appointed Amcazade Hüseyin Pasha as grand vizier. Amcazade's successful administration and his role in ending the wars with the Treaty of Karlowitz in 1699 were significant achievements; yet his appointments based on his own circle displeased members of the palace establishment.

During this period, Feyzullah Efendi became a decisive force in palace politics, controlling positions within the religious-judicial hierarchy (*ilmiyye*) and balancing the influence of the grand vizier. As alternative power searches within palace circles led to executions and exiles, the struggle for power paved the way for the Edirne Incident.¹⁴

Şeyhülislam Feyzullah Efendi'nin şeyhüislamlığı döneminde veziriazamlık makamında Amcazade Hüseyin Paşa bulunuyordu. II. Mustafa'nın verdiği yetkilerle Feyzullah Efendi, veziriazamın

¹³ Tahir Sevinç, "Mustafa'nın İktidar Mücadelesi ve 1703 Edirne İsyanıyla Tahttan İndirilmesi" [*Mustafa's Struggle for Power and His Deposition during the 1703 Edirne Rebellion*], *Osmanlı Mirası Araştırmaları Dergisi (OMAD)* 4, no. 9 (July 2017): 28.

¹⁴ Rifa'at Ali Abou-El-Haj, "The Narcissism of Mustafa II (1695–1703): A Psychohistorical Study," *Studia Islamica*.

yetkilerini ve nüfuzunu bastırmaya çalıştı. Bu süreçte Nezir Ağa da ona destek verdi. Donanma komutanlığındaki bir atama girişimi yüzünden veziriazam ile şeyhülislam arasında gerilim arttı.

Amcazade Hüseyin Paşa'nın kendi adamlarını göreve getirme çabaları padişah tarafından engellendi. Bunun üzerine veziriazam, II. Mustafa yerine Şehzade Ahmed'i tahta çıkarmayı planladı; ancak bu girişim ortaya çıkarılınca ilgili kişiler idam veya sürgün edildi. Yaşanan gelişmeler, Amcazade Hüseyin Paşa'nın hastalanarak görevden çekilmesine yol açtı.

Onun yerine, şeyhülislamın desteğiyle 1702'de Daltaban Mustafa Paşa veziriazam oldu. Ancak o da görevinde serbest hareket edemedi; atamalarına müdahale edildi ve giderek Feyzullah Efendi'nin baskısı altında kaldı. Nüfuzunu artırmak isteyen Daltaban Mustafa Paşa, Karlofça Antlaşması sonrası dengeleri bozabilecek askerî girişimler planladıysa da bu durum diplomatik kriz yarattı. Rus elçisinin uyarıları ve Kırım Hanı'nın ifadeleri üzerine sorumluluk veziriazama yüklendi. Sonuçta Daltaban Mustafa Paşa idam edildi, malları müsadere edilerek hazineye aktarıldı.¹⁵ He gained trust in state administration. Although he was envied during the tenure of Daltaban Mustafa Pasha, his rise continued once he secured the support of the grand vizier and the şeyhülislam. With his appointment to the grand vizierate, the empire briefly entered a period in which grand viziers were chosen from among scribal (kalemiyye) bureaucrats. However, his term was short; when appointing him, Mustafa II particularly emphasized that he should follow the advice of the şeyhülislam.

Although Rami Mehmed Pasha and Feyzullah Efendi initially shared similar views on state affairs, relations between them gradually deteriorated. Feyzullah Efendi's increasing influence and favoritism toward his close circle caused discomfort in governance. Rami Mehmed Pasha, in terms of balancing power, cooperated with Moralı Hasan Pasha. This المعارضة circle took advantage of the unrest that began in 1703 when some soldiers assigned to the Georgian campaign refused to go. To accelerate the process, former Surre Emini İbrahim Ağa was sent to Istanbul with the rank of cebecibaşı. Thus, the power struggle within palace circles moved toward open rebellion.

After Feyzullah Efendi was appointed şeyhülislam for the second time, his influence over state administration became even more pronounced. In a short time, he accumulated considerable wealth and appointed his sons—who lacked sufficient seniority—to high-ranking positions within the religious-judicial hierarchy (ilmiyye), causing unrest within the bureaucracy. His attempts to maintain the office of şeyhülislam within his family were seen as contrary to both tradition and merit, provoking strong reactions.

While these developments were unfolding, Mustafa II moved to Edirne following the Treaty of Karlowitz due to diplomatic and administrative matters. However, this ceased to be a temporary visit; as members of the palace and state elite also settled there, Edirne effectively became a second center of administration. The sultan's prolonged absence from İstanbul, his focus on hunting, and delays in soldiers' salaries increased dissatisfaction among both the military and the people of İstanbul. As tradesmen in the capital were deprived of the expenditures of the palace and state officials, economic stagnation began to be felt. Thus, a latent rivalry emerged between İstanbul and Edirne as centers of power.

The planned Georgian campaign in 1703 further aggravated the already tense atmosphere. Some soldiers who had not received their ulufe (stipends) refused to join the campaign and revolted. Investigations revealed misconduct by certain officials, leading to dismissals and reassignments; however, these measures were insufficient to suppress the rebellion. Figures such as İbrahim Ağa

15 Abou-El-Haj, "Vezir and Paşa Households," 445–47.

played notable roles in directing the uprising. Soon, Janissaries, members of the ulema, and broad segments of the populace joined the rebels; when prisoners in Istanbul were released, incidents of looting increased.

As the wave of rebellion advanced toward Edirne, government forces confronted the insurgents. However, when a significant portion of the army changed sides, the balance shifted, leaving Mustafa II without adequate military support. Realizing that resistance was no longer possible, he was forced to abdicate. In his place, his brother Şehzade Ahmed was proclaimed sultan and ascended the throne in 1703 as Ahmed III. The new sultan sought to restore order in the short term by appointing some of the leading figures of the rebellion to important positions.¹⁶

The Patrona Halil Rebellion

The Patrona Halil rebellion is often said to have occurred due to moral decline. In reality, however, the main issue was once again the clash of interest groups. Bureaucrats who had been dismissed from office and had lost their influence revolted against authority and reflected this discontent onto the public. Propaganda carried out through sermons and religious discourse helped frame opposition to the government as legitimate. In particular, the provocative language of certain preachers accelerated the process.

During this period, the general condition of the population was poor. Diseases and epidemics were widespread. Moreover, banditry had increased in Anatolia and Rumelia. Migration from villages to cities accelerated; while agricultural production declined, unemployment in urban centers rose. In İstanbul, competition among tradesmen intensified, and Janissaries engaged in commerce further disrupted economic balances.

Developments in foreign policy also reduced public confidence in the state. Unsuccessful campaigns in Iran, claims that troops had retreated in Russia, and the sultan's reluctance to personally lead campaigns disturbed both the army and the populace.

In fact, the rebellion had been planned in advance. The initial attempt was postponed due to unfavorable conditions, but shortly afterward the movement began under the leadership of the Janissaries. Some segments of the artisan class also offered support. As Patrona Halil and his associates came to the forefront, it became clear that certain religious figures played a guiding role behind the scenes.

The rebels toured the bazaars, calling the public to join them. Shops closed, the crowd grew, and they gathered at Et Meydanı. The absence of many state officials from the city created a power vacuum. Although the Janissary Agha attempted to calm the crowd, he was unsuccessful. The rebels stormed prisons, released prisoners, and increased their strength.

When looting began, the leaders of the uprising tried to bring it under control, as they did not want to damage the movement's claim of "reform." Their aim was not mere plunder, but to present their actions as a justified reaction against misrule.

16 Tahir Sevinç, "Mustafa'nın İktidar Mücadelesi ve 1703 Edirne İsyanıyla Tahttan İndirilmesi" [Mustafa's Struggle for Power and His Deposition during the 1703 Edirne Rebellion], *Osmanlı Mirası Araştırmaları Dergisi (OMAD)* 4, no. 9 (July 2017): 29–30.

Eventually, the crowd marched toward the palace. As pressure mounted, the sultan was forced to consent to the execution of the grand vizier Nevşehirli Damat İbrahim Pasha and his circle, who were targeted by the rebels. However, this did not satisfy them. Rumors and provocations continued. In the end, the rebels compelled Ahmed III to abdicate. He was succeeded by Mahmud I.

For a time during the new reign, Patrona Halil and his circle remained influential. Yet it soon became evident that they, too, were pursuing their own interests. Seeking to reestablish state authority, Mahmud I seized an opportunity to summon Patrona Halil and his leading associates to the palace and had them eliminated. Subsequent minor uprisings were swiftly suppressed.

Thus, the Patrona Halil Rebellion entered history not merely as a popular reaction, but as a major political crisis shaped by the convergence of economic hardship, military failures, and the struggle of competing interest groups.¹⁷

The Kabakçı Mustafa Rebellion

Selim III decided that the Nizam-i Cedid Army would also be assigned to the Bosphorus fortresses, and that the yamak auxiliaries and Janissaries would be incorporated into these new units. However, the yamaks objected, and instead of easing tensions, Musa Köse Pasha aggravated them. On the one hand, he ordered the yamaks to wear the Nizam-ı Cedid uniform; on the other, he allowed rumors to spread that wearing such clothing would amount to abandoning Islam. The yamaks, already inclined toward unrest, refused to wear the uniforms. They resisted their commanders, declaring: “We are Janissaries, sons of Janissaries; we do not drill like infidel soldiers.”

Within a short time, they killed Halil Haseki and the Bosphorus Superintendent Mahmud Raif Efendi, who had tried to suppress the unrest. Thus, long-simmering discontent turned into open rebellion under the pretext of uniforms.

When news of the uprising reached the Sublime Porte, Musa Pasha downplayed the seriousness of the events in a council meeting. In reality, he had secretly instructed that neither the Nizam-ı Cedid troops nor the artillery should intervene against the rebels. The true nature of the uprising was not fully conveyed to Selim III, who believed it to be merely a minor disturbance.

Leading the rebellion was Kabakçı Mustafa. Though not formally educated, he stood out for his courage and harsh demeanor. Among his associates were figures such as Arnavut Ali, Bayburtlu Süleyman, and Memiş Çavuş. The rebels swore not to harm the public and not to disperse until their demands were met. While they ostensibly demanded the punishment of reforms they considered contrary to Islamic law, their true aim was to abolish the Nizam-ı Cedid. Calling out, “Let whoever is Muslim and considers himself a member of the corps join us,” they gathered at Et Meydanı.

Although Selim III was deeply saddened by these developments, he avoided decisive military intervention to prevent bloodshed. Since the empire was already at war with Russia, he did not deem it appropriate to summon the army to Istanbul. He became increasingly isolated within the palace, while some statesmen and religious circles secretly supported the rebels.

17 H. Mustafa Eravcı and İlker Kiremit, “Lale Dönemi ve Patrona Halil İsyanı Üzerine Yeni Değerlendirmeler” [New Evaluations on the Tulip Era and the Patrona Halil Rebellion], *Tarih Okulu Dergisi* VIII (2010): 83–90.

As Janissaries, unemployed groups, and dissatisfied tradesmen joined the crowd at Et Meydanı, the rebellion quickly expanded. The rebels demanded the abolition of the Nizam-ı Cedid and the execution of certain state officials. In order to prevent further bloodshed, Selim III accepted these demands. However, contrary to expectations, this decision did not halt the violence. Many of the officials whose names appeared on the list were captured and killed.

Those executed were experienced administrators, particularly needed during the ongoing war with Russia. Their loss represented a serious weakening of the state.

In the end, the Kabakçı Mustafa Rebellion was not merely a military uprising; it became a significant turning point in which interest groups organized against reform movements used religious rhetoric and military discontent to undermine central authority.¹⁸

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When news of the uprising reached the Sublime Porte, Musa Pasha downplayed the seriousness of the events in a council meeting. In reality, he had secretly instructed that neither the Nizam-ı Cedid troops nor the artillery should intervene against the rebels. The true *maçıbe* of the uprising was not fully conveyed to Selim III, who believed it to be merely a minor disturbance.

Leading the rebellion was Kabakçı Mustafa. Though not formally educated, he stood out for his courage and harsh demeanor. Among his associates were figures such as Arnavut Ali, Bayburtlu Süleyman, and Memiş Çavuş. The rebels swore not to harm the public and not to disperse until their demands were met. While they ostensibly demanded the punishment of reforms they considered contrary to Islamic law, their true aim was to abolish the Nizam-ı Cedid. Calling out, “Let whoever is Muslim and considers himself a member of the corps join us,” they gathered at Et Meydanı.

Although Selim III was deeply saddened by these developments, he avoided decisive military intervention to prevent bloodshed. Since the empire was already at war with Russia, he did not deem it appropriate to summon the army to Istanbul. He became increasingly isolated within the palace, while some statesmen and religious circles secretly supported the rebels.

As Janissaries, unemployed groups, and dissatisfied tradesmen joined the crowd at Et Meydanı, the rebellion quickly expanded. The rebels demanded the abolition of the Nizam-ı Cedid and the execution of certain state officials. In order to prevent further bloodshed, Selim III accepted these

18 A. Saydam, *Algı Yönetimi ile Darbe Yapmak: 1807–1808 Yıllarında İstanbul’da Siyasî Kargaşa* [Making a Coup through Perception Management: Political Turmoil in Istanbul, 1807–1808], 734–36.

demands. However, contrary to expectations, this decision did not halt the violence. Many of the officials whose names appeared on the list were captured and killed.

Those executed were experienced administrators, particularly needed during the ongoing war with Russia. Their loss represented a serious weakening of the state.

In the end, the Kabakçı Mustafa Rebellion was not merely a military uprising; it became a significant turning point in which interest groups organized against reform movements used religious rhetoric and military discontent to undermine central authority.¹⁹

The Coup of Abdülaziz (1876)

Abdulaziz was a well-educated sultan with a strong interest in sports. He practiced swimming, wrestling, javelin throwing (cirit), and horseback riding. Contrary to common misconceptions, he was not opposed to Europe; rather, he maintained a more traditional outlook in his inner life and daily practices.

His preference for traditional performances such as ortaoyunu instead of Western-style theater, along with his interest in wrestling and cirit, led him to be regarded as a “people’s sultan.”²⁰

When Abdulaziz ascended the throne on 25 June 1861, a significant portion of the public was pleased with him.

In the early years of his reign, influenced by the trauma of the loss of Crimea, he made major investments in the navy and established scholarship-supported schools. Railway lines and telegraph networks were expanded. However, because these military, naval, and technical investments were largely financed through foreign borrowing, the empire’s financial balance gradually deteriorated.²¹

The relationship between statesmen and Abdulaziz was neither balanced nor stable. Grand viziers were frequently replaced. Allegations were spread about his private life, portraying him as “fond of entertainment.” In contrast, he sought to maintain contact with the public, undertook provincial tours, and supported religious and social institutions.

Nevertheless, rising foreign debt, uprisings in the Balkans, and increasing pressure from Europe intensified over time. As a result, he paid official visits to France and United Kingdom, and the revolt launched with the aim of annexing Crete to Greece was eventually brought to an end.²²

Although these visits brought a degree of diplomatic easing, they were not sufficient to resolve internal problems. As the economic crisis deepened, opposition circles within the state increasingly agreed that Abdulaziz was not governing the country effectively. Among these figures were Mithat Pasha and his associates.

The Young Ottomans (often associated with the broader reformist press movement later linked to the Young Turks) were highly influential in the press. Through newspapers, Abdülaziz’s rule was

19 A. Topaloğlu, “VAJDA, Georges,” *TDV İslâm Ansiklopedisi* (2012): 454–57.

20 Hikmet Toker, “Sultan Abdülaziz’in Müzisyen Kişiliğiyle İlgili İngiltere’de Yayınlanmış Bir Makale ‘Sultan and His Music’” [An Article Published in England on Sultan Abdülaziz’s Musical Personality: “Sultan and His Music”], *Milli Saraylar Dergisi*, no. 10 (Istanbul, 2013): 166.

21 *Telakki Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi* 4, no. 6 (Summer 2025): 3–4.

22 *Telakki Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi* 4, no.

harshly criticized, and rumors were spread claiming that he had lost his mental balance. With the support of student movements and segments of the bureaucracy, the groundwork for a coup was prepared. Going even further, they requested that the şeyhülislam conduct an inquiry into the sultan's sanity and issue a fatwa based on alleged evidence declaring him unfit to rule. The şeyhülislam responded favorably and issued the fatwa.²³

In May 1876, through the cooperation of a military and civilian coalition, Abdülaziz was deposed and replaced by Murad V. Abdülaziz was forced to submit to this decision. He was first held under supervision in Topkapı Palace and later transferred to Feriye Palace. The treatment of his entourage and family deeply affected both him and his mother. The manner of his deposition and the events that followed became one of the most controversial and dramatic transfers of power in Ottoman history.

Abdülaziz reportedly requested scissors for trimming his beard; afterward, sounds were heard from the locked room where he was being kept. Soon after, the former sultan was found dead. Although doctors wished to perform an autopsy, permission was denied, and the matter was effectively covered up. During the reign of Abdul Hamid II, the Yıldız Investigation would later be launched to reexamine the incident.

The Deposition of Murad V and the Accession of Abdul Hamid II

After Abdülaziz was dethroned, Murad V ascended the throne. This event was regarded as the first clear coup in Ottoman history in which public opinion and a bureaucratic alliance played a decisive role.

Murad V was welcomed by the circles that had deposed Abdülaziz due to his liberal views. However, the suspicious death of Abdülaziz and the subsequent Çerkes Hasan raid deeply affected his mental health. Doctors brought from Europe reported that his recovery would take time. At a moment when the state faced severe internal and external crises, prolonged uncertainty was deemed unacceptable. During this period, Şehzade Abdülhamid emerged as a key figure, gaining support on the condition that if he accepted Murad V would not recover sufficiently to rule.

On 31 August 1876, Murad V was formally deposed and Abdul Hamid II ascended the throne. Abdul Hamid II swiftly purged many officials from office; however, this newly consolidated cadre would not remain intact for long, and in later years figures such as Mahmud Shevket Pasha would engage in significant opposition activities against him.²⁴

Coup Mechanisms Against Abdulhamid II

The reign of **Abdulhamid II** was a long and difficult period in which the Ottoman Empire struggled with both territorial losses and internal political crises. After the Russo-Turkish War, the balance of power in the Balkans shifted. European states increasingly intervened in Ottoman internal affairs under the pretext of protecting Christian subjects. In this environment, Abdulhamid II chose to govern the state through strong centralization and established strict mechanisms of

²³ Mehmet Ali Beyhan, "a.g.m.," 106.

²⁴ Murat Yılmaz, "Jön Türk Muhalefesinde Osmanlı'nın Meşrû Hükümdarı: V. Murâd" [The Legitimate Ottoman Ruler in the Young Turk Opposition: Murad V], *Osmanlı Medeniyeti Araştırmaları Dergisi* no. 17 (June 2023): 204–18.

control. Press censorship, an extensive spy network, and the exile of dissidents became fundamental instruments of governance.

This repressive regime provoked opposition among students of the new-generation schools and young officers. Those educated in institutions such as the Military Academy and the School of Civil Administration were familiar with constitutional systems in the West and debated the causes of Ottoman decline. In their view, the solution lay in restoring a constitutional regime in which the sultan's powers were limited and parliament reconvened.

The most significant secret organization formed around these ideas was the Committee of Union and Progress (CUP), founded in 1889. Initially emerging among students, the movement gradually gained support among bureaucrats and military officers. Due to strict surveillance in Istanbul, some members fled to Europe. In cities such as Paris, Geneva, and Cairo, they organized and published opposition newspapers.

The movement's principal base, however, became Salonika. Salonika and Monastir were advantageous due to their multiethnic structure and strong military presence. Young officers stationed there were dealing with nationalist uprisings while also believing that the central government was weak. For them, constitutionalism was the remedy that could save the state.

After 1906, the Committee of Union and Progress organized itself through a cell system, particularly within the Third Army. At the 1907 Paris Congress, closer cooperation was established between European-based opposition figures and cadres in Rumelia. The objective was clear: to restore the 1876 constitution.

By the summer of 1908, external developments further heightened tensions. The meeting between King Edward VII of Britain and Tsar Nicholas II of Russia in Reval was widely perceived as concerning Ottoman territories. Fearing the loss of the Balkans, young officers accelerated their actions. In July 1908, events began in earnest when Resneli Niyazi Bey took to the mountains with his troops, demanding the reinstatement of the constitution. Shortly afterward, Enver Pasha joined the movement. Other officers followed in coordinated fashion, and soon much of Rumelia came under the control of pro-CUP forces.

Telegrams were sent to Istanbul demanding the re-proclamation of constitutional rule. What had begun as an intellectual movement had transformed into direct military pressure. As some units sent from the capital also joined the rebels, the government found it increasingly difficult to maintain control. Concerned that the crisis might escalate into civil war—and aware that a significant portion of the army supported the CUP—Abdulhamid II ultimately stepped back. On 23 July 1908, the constitution was reinstated, marking the proclamation of the Second Constitutional Era.

The parliament (Meclis-i Mebusan) reopened, elections were held, and the constitutional system that had long been suspended resumed functioning. Across the empire, the event was celebrated with great enthusiasm. "Liberty" became the defining word of the era.

Initially, constitutionalism carried different hopes for different groups. Intellectuals expected freedom of the press and thought, while various ethnic communities anticipated expanded rights. Yet political competition soon intensified. As the Committee of Union and Progress became more organized and influential, opposition groups also mobilized.

This tension culminated in the 31 March Incident. The uprising, initiated by certain military units in Istanbul, was seen as a reactionary movement against constitutional rule. The Action Army (Hareket

Ordusu), advancing from Salonika, suppressed the revolt. Subsequently, Abdulhamid II was deposed and replaced by Mehmed V.²⁵

Republican Period and Military Interventions

In the Ottoman Empire, many sultans were deposed through the intervention of military and bureaucratic power groups. Although the regime changed during the Republican era, debates over military tutelage remained on the political agenda for many years. While the Republic emphasized a break with the Ottoman past at the level of discourse, the influence of the military bureaucracy on the political system was at times decisive.

In Turkey, secularization differed from Western societies, where it developed largely through social transformation. Instead, it was implemented from the top down under the leadership of state elites who regarded secularization and Westernization as necessary. For this reason, Westernization in Turkey assumed a state-centered rather than individual-centered character. For many years, the boundaries of political life and freedoms were shaped by military and civilian bureaucratic elites.

Over time, military tutelage became more institutionalized and embedded within the constitutional system. Institutions such as the National Security Council and the Constitutional Court became key components of the political structure. After each military intervention, new constitutional arrangements were introduced and the system was restructured.

Military interventions in Turkey were generally justified with the claim of “saving the country from chaos.” The most significant interventions include the following:

The 1960 Turkish coup d'état was the first military intervention of the multi-party era. İsmet İnönü played a significant role in the transition to multi-party politics. In subsequent elections, the Democrat Party came to power. During the later years of Prime Minister Adnan Menderes's rule, rising political tensions and criticisms accelerated the coup process. After the coup, President Celal Bayar and Prime Minister Menderes were arrested; Menderes was executed in 1961.

The 1971 Turkish military memorandum took the form of a military memorandum rather than a direct takeover. The political instability and right–left clashes of the 1970s prepared the ground for this intervention. Following the memorandum, the government resigned, but political and social problems persisted.

The 1980 Turkish coup d'état occurred amid escalating violence and political deadlock. After the coup, the constitution was suspended, political parties were closed, and the 1982 Constitution was enacted. This period marked direct military rule.

The 1997 Turkish military memorandum is often described as a “post-modern coup.” Although the military did not directly seize power, strong pressure was exerted on the government through bureaucratic mechanisms. Debates over religious identity and the public sphere became particularly prominent during this period.

²⁵ Ahmet Şimşirgil, *Kayı IX: II. Abdülhamid Han* [Kayı IX: Sultan Abdulhamid II] (Istanbul: Timaş Yayınları, 2018), 192–221.

The 2007 Turkish e-memorandum emerged as a statement published on the website of the Chief of General Staff. It is considered an important turning point in the transformation of civil–military relations in Turkey.

The 2016 Turkish coup attempt differed from previous interventions in that it failed. Turkish authorities stated that the attempt was organized by members of FETÖ. Security forces and civilians acted together against the attempt. Parliament and various state institutions were targeted; as a result of the clashes, many people lost their lives and thousands were injured. The mass public resistance against the coup attempt is widely regarded as a significant turning point in Turkey’s democratic history.

Overall, military interventions have constituted major turning points in Turkey’s political history. At the same time, over the years, efforts have been made to strengthen democratic mechanisms and expand the sphere of civilian politics.²⁶

Conclusion

The historical process demonstrates that coups in both the Ottoman and Republican periods generally emerged from political crises and struggles for power within the system. In the Ottoman era, interventions were often shaped by struggles among princes and palace-centered military power balances. In the modern period, however, coups were carried out on more institutional and ideological grounds.

The accession of figures such as Selim I (Yavuz Sultan Selim) may have resolved certain immediate state problems; yet other interventions driven by rival power groups—particularly factions within the palace—contributed to long-term instability and decline. In both periods, coups tended to produce short-term solutions but created new structural problems in the long run.

This pattern suggests that lasting political stability can only be achieved through strong institutions, constitutional order, and the rule of law rather than through power struggles or extra-legal interventions.

26 Ali Aygün, “Türkiye’de Darbeler ve 15 Temmuz” [Coups in Turkey and July 15], 1–3.

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